

REPLACE THERMAL COATINGS WHEN HEATING BUILDINGS

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Abstract: The paper presents the findings of experimental investigations on the evaluation and enhancement of the current techniques for calculating thermal conductivity. Techniques for effectively using heat are emphasized, such as applying coatings that completely retain heat on non-textured surfaces.

Key words: *energy efficiency, advantages and areas of application of liquid heat-retaining coatings, microsphere, modern heat-retaining coatings, thermal conductivity, requirements for heat-retaining coatings*

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Introduction

The efficient use of heat and lowering building energy consumption are two of the most crucial and urgent problems facing the construction sector today. One of the top priorities is to effectively utilise heat energy in buildings, heat pipes, energy networks, and other areas. This is because energy supplies are scarce, energy is expensive, and producing it has a bad effect on the environment.

In the current environment of rising costs and a dearth of conventional energy sources, the utilization of contemporary heat-insulating materials—including liquid energy-storing heat-insulating coatings—is crucial study. Many people's attention has recently been drawn to heat-insulating paints made from hollow ceramic, glass, and polymer microspheres.

The Fergana Polytechnic Institute's "Youth Innovative Technology Center" is conducting research to enhance the procedure for calculating the coefficient of thermal conductivity of heat-retaining coatings.

The interior preservation and protection of heat, heat and engineering networks, technological pipelines, heat energy and capacity equipment, thermal insulation, waterproofing, protection from erosion (corrosion), and construction are all uses for this paint. It is also used to preserve and protect the facades of residential and production industrial buildings. designed for use in building.

Analysis

The paint's composition is created using an acrylic binder, entire filler, and additional ingredients in the form of hollow microspheres.

The operation of "classic" heaters and heat insulators with hollow microspheres in their composition differ substantially in terms of how they work. The material provides a significant energy-saving outcome even at a thickness of 1 mm because of its special characteristics.

Even in difficult domains, it is quite simple to apply. You can apply liquid thermal insulation to the surface of your choice in a number of ways. Simply select the option that best matches your needs. You can make use of brushes, rollers, and other equipment.

Use a brush to remove dust, mold, and oil from concrete surfaces; clean and degrease the metal surface as well. It is advised to use a phosphating agent to cure any rust spots on the metal. The wood should be primed with primer and biocides before installing the insulation. If you are redoing the brick surface, you must first prime it before plastering it.

Picture 1. The results of the experiment

Method

A heat-insulating coating is used on a variety of surfaces, including metal, concrete, brick, wood, and plastic. The surface is first cleaned, primed if necessary, and then the same mixture is diluted with water (no more than 5%), acrylic paint, or a liquid glass mixture, depending on the application.

On a wet, snowy surface, the mixture cannot be dispersed. There are multiple layers of mixture set down. Depending on the activities and objectives, the appropriate number of layers is chosen. Between drying layers, it may be reapplied many times. Depending on the temperature of the heat carrier and the desired surface temperature, the ultimate coating thickness is chosen.

Using a brush, spatula, roller, or sprayer, the coating is readily sprayed (laid) on the surface of any geometric shape. No dangerous substances are released into the atmosphere by the coating.

When working outside or in a vented space, a respirator is not required, however it is advised when working in a non-ventilated building. 750–1000 g/m² is the typical consumption for a dry coating layer that is 1 mm thick.

The inspection was outdoors. The coating is laid in 3 layers. The final thickness was 3 mm. The total coating consumption was 0.9 liters.

Conclusion

Let's sum up by saying that one of the most important issues of the day is conserving heat. It works particularly well when used on contemporary homes that are still under development. Although the winter months are short in our nation, this covering helps retain summertime coolness as well as heat.

References

1. Qo'chqarov, B. U., Tojiboyev, B. T., & Axtambayev, S. S. (2021). Experimental determination of the gas consumption sent to the device for wet dusting in the humid mode. *Экономика и социум*, (6-1), 226-229.
2. Маткаримов, Ш. А., Зияев, А. Т., Тожибоев, Б. Т., & Кучкаров, Б. У. (2020). ПОКРЫТИЕ ЗАДВИЖЕК И ЗАПОРНОЙ АРМАТУРЫ ТЕПЛОВЫХ СЕТЕЙ ЖИДКИМ ТЕПЛОИЗОЛЯЦИОННЫМ ПОКРЫТИЕМ. *Universum: технические науки*, (12-5 (81)).
3. Boburjon Tolibjonovich Tojiboyev (2021). HEAT RESISTANT FLUID INSULATING COAT. *Scientific progress*, 2 (7), 524-531.
4. Эргашев Насимбек Ахмаджонович, Маткаримов Шухрат Адхамович, Зияев Абдукарим Ташпулатович, Тожибоев Бобир Толибжонович, & Кучкаров Бобирмирзо Улугбекович (2019). Опытное определение расхода газа, подаваемое на пылеочищающую установку с контактным элементом, работающим в режиме спутникового вихря. *Universum: технические науки*, (12-1 (69)), 29-31.
5. Халилов, Ш. З., Тожибоев, Б. Т., Умаров, Э. С., & Кучкоров, Б. У. (2019). Прием и хранение зерновой смеси, поступающей после комбайнов. *Журнал Технических исследований*, (2).
6. Tojiev, R., Ortikaliyev, B., & Tojiboyev, B. (2019). Improving selecting technology of raw materials of fireproof bricks. *Тенденции и перспективы развития науки и образования в условиях глобализации. Украина*, 27(46), 606-609.
7. Tojiboyev, B. T. (2020). EUPHEMISM AND GENDER: LINGUOCULTURAL EUPHEMISMS AMONG MALES AND FEMALES IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF DISCOURSE ON INNOVATION, INTEGRATION AND EDUCATION*, 1(5), 8-11.
8. Халилов, Ш. З., Тожибоев, Б. Т., & Кучкаров, Б. У. (2020). Причина скачков при трении. *Журнал Технических исследований*, 3(1).
9. Tojiboyev, B. T., & Mo, A. A. O. G. L. (2021). LIQUID COMPOSITION HEAT INSULATING COATS AND METHODS FOR DETERMINATION OF THEIR HEAT CONDUCTIVITY. *Scientific progress*, 2(6), 1628-1634.
10. Tojiboyev, B. T., & Alijon o'g'li, M. B. (2020). SOME QUESTIONS OF SUFFIXATION, IMPACT AND ALTERNATION BY THE BACKGROUND IN BORROWED WORDS WITH THE VALUE OF A FACE IN RUSSIAN. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF DISCOURSE ON INNOVATION, INTEGRATION AND EDUCATION*, 1(5), 71-77.
11. Tojiboyev, B. T., & Gapporov, Q. G. ugli Rahmonov, AT (2020). Reception and Storage of Grain Mixture Generated After the Combines. *International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS)*. www.ijeais.org/ijeais, ISSN, 96-100.
12. Мирзаходжаев, Ш. Ш., Тожибоев, Б. Т., & Ахмедов, Р. Р. (2019). ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ОПЫТНОГО ОБРАЗЦА КОМБИНИРОВАННОГО ФРОНТАЛЬНОГО ПЛУГА С АКТИВНЫМИ РАБОЧИМИ ОРГАНАМИ. In *КОНЦЕПЦИИ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ НАУКИ В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ УСЛОВИЯХ* (pp. 46-48).

13. Toshpo'latovich, Z. A., & Tolibjonovich, T. B. (2021). Calculation of Thermal State of Sleeves and Cylinder Covers. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCES*, 2(11), 229-236.
14. Boburjon Tolibjonovich Tojiboyev (2021). HEAT RESISTANT FLUID INSULATING COAT. *Scientific progress*, 2 (7), 524-531.
15. Нишонова, Ф. Ф., & Жалилова, Г. Х. Қ. (2021). Материал қатламини сақлаш учун сарфланган қувват ҳисоби. *Scientific progress*, 2(6), 166-170.
16. Ахунбаев, А. А., Нишонова, Ф. Ф., & Жалилова, Г. Х. Қ. (2021). ҚУРИТИШ АППАРАТЛАРИДА МАТЕРИАЛ ҚАТЛАМИНИ САҚЛАШ УЧУН САРФЛАНГАН ҚУВВАТ ҲИСОБИ. *Scientific progress*, 2(6), 1624-1627.
17. Abduqodirov, N. S. O., Oqyolov, K. R. O., Jalilova, G. X. Q., & Nishonova, G. G. (2021). Causes and extinguishing equipment of vibrations occurred by machinery and mechanisms. *Scientific progress*, 2(2), 950-953.
18. Abduqodirov, N. S. O. G. L., Oqyo'lov, K. R. O. G., & Jalilova, G. X. Q. (2021). Paxta xomashyosini quritish va tozalash. *Scientific progress*, 2(1), 857-861.
19. Yunus, M., Sobitjon, A., Nurzod, A., & Gulnoza, J. (2021). RESEARCH OF PARAMETERS AT THE APPEARANCE OF SHEARING FORCES IN THE COMPOUND TENSION ROLLER OF TRANSPORTATION AND TECHNOLOGICAL MACHINES. *Universum: технические науки*, (11-6 (92)), 5-11.
20. Tojiboyev, B. T., & qizi Askarova, M. B. (2023). ARCHITECTURE AND LANDSCAPE OF FERGANA CITY. *GOLDEN BRAIN*, 1(13), 403-408.
21. Tojiboyev, B., & Mullajonova, M. (2024). REASONABLE USE OF HEAT AND HEAT CONDUCTIVITY PROPERTIES OF HEAT PRESERVING COATINGS. *International Journal of Advance Scientific Research*, 4(03), 96-101.
22. Tolibjonovich, T. B. (2024). ENERGY-SAVING MATERIALS AND PROSPECTS OF THEIR APPLICATION TO BUILDING CONSTRUCTION. *Western European Journal of Modern Experiments and Scientific Methods*, 2(2), 29-33.